

Original Research Report

Assessment of Nutritional Status of Nursery School Children in Obudu Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study assessed the nutritional status of nursery school children aged 2-6 years in Obudu Local Government of Cross River State, three research questions guided the study. The assessment utilized the socioeconomics, and education status of parents, eating habits of the children, anthropometric measurement, and chemical signs (Scantiness and fluffiness of hair, paleness of lips /tongue, protrusion of stomach, flatness of buttocks, oedema and general fitness). It was found that the eating habits of the children (45.5%) were determined by the availability of mainly carbohydrate foods and 18.2% of proteins, vitamins, and minerals. The habits were due to the poor socio-economic and educational status of the parents. The result of anthropometric measurements indicated that on weight-for-height status, 10.8% of the children were wasted with a high prevalence rate of 5.9% in male children whereas females 4.9%. The sex of the children did not significantly influence the weight-for-height status of the children ($p>0.5$). In terms of height-for-age status, 10.8% were stunted. There was no significant difference in the sex of the children ($p>0.5$). Weight-for-age indicated that 5.9% of the children were underweight. A higher prevalence rate (3.9%) was observed among the males than the females (2.0%). There was no significant difference in sex $p>0.5$, overweight children were 8.8%, females being higher at 5.9% while males were over 2.9%. Using clinical signs, it was observed that 12.7% of the children were generally unfit. The children with scanty hair 10.8%, fluffy hair 2.0%, paleness of lips/tongue, 4.9%, protruded stomach 10.8%, flattened buttocks 11.8%, Oedema 4.9%. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that children should be made to eat 3-5 meals daily including 2-3 servings of snacks to enhance their nutritional status.

Keywords: Anthropometry, Assessment, Malnutrition, Nutrition, Nutritional Status, Nursery School Children

1. Introduction

Nutritional status refers to health and well-being of individuals and population as influenced by their intake and utilization of nutrients. Nutritional status is the nutritional health of a person as determined by anthropometric measurements (height & weight) biochemical measurements of nutrient or their byproducts in blood and urine, a clinical (physical) examination and dietary analysis Wardlaw et al. (2020). According to the author, three general categories of nutritional status were recognized, the desirable nutrition, under nutrition and over nutrition. The nutritional status for a particular nutrient is desirable when body tissues have enough of the nutrient to support normal metabolic functions as well as surplus stores that can be mobilized in times of increased need. A desirable nutritional status can be achieved by obtaining essential nutrients from a variety of foods. Under nutrition results when nutrient intake does not meet nutrient need. Stores of the nutrients become depleted by ongoing body use, some sooner than others. The demand for these nutrients exists partly because much of the body is in a constant state of turnover. In the case over nutrition, it is caused by prolonged consumption of more nutrients than the body needs. For instance, a few weeks or months over nutrition may cause no signs or symptoms.

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Nutritional assessment either completely or in part is the process of measuring the nutritional health of an individual by analyzing background factors and evaluating the ABCDEs, (Anthropometric measurement, Biochemical assessment, Clinical examination, Dietary history and Economic status). Background factors include family history which plays an important role in determining nutritional and health status; other components include a medical history especially for any disease\ status or treatments such as medications that could impede nutrient absorptive processes or ultimate use, economic and appropriate food needed to maintain health, and educational attainment to determine the degree of complexity that can be used in written materials and oral discussions Wardlaw, Hampl and Disilevestro (2004).

Evaluating the ABCDEs entails anthropometric measurement, biochemical assessment, clinical examination, dietary analysis and economic status Casadei and Kiel (2022).

Anthropometric assessment includes measurement of height, weight, skin fold thickness, arm circumference and other parameters, while biochemical (laboratory) assessment entails assessing blood and urine, which include enzyme activities, concentration of nutrient or their by-products. Clinical (physical) examination entails general appearance of skin, eyes and tongue, rapid hair loss, sense of touch and ability to walk, whereas diet history requires information on usual intake or record of previous day's meals. Economic status is the purchasing ability of family as regards access to adequate diet.

World Health Organization WHO (2010), United Nations Children emergency fund UNICEF (2012) and other world bodies place so much emphasis on the health of mothers and children, especially under five children. Results show that infants up to the age of 10 months have a better nutritional status than older children. McBean and Miller (2010) stated that by the age of three years a child is more than twice as likely to be under-weight as a 10 months old Morrison et al. (2002). Again, there is a negative association between age and the nutritional status at that age. The nutritional health of a person as determined by anthropometric measurements (height, weight) biochemical measurement of nutrients or their by-product of urine and blood, a clinical (physical) examination and a dietary analysis.

In view of the above fact and considering the rapid growth, rate that characterized infancy, growth cases quickly during age 2-6 years. In this country, it coincides with pre-nursery and nursery schooling. Growth rate declines, eating behaviour changes and decreased growth rate leads to a decreased appetite as against infants who are still breast-feeding. Owing to this reduced appetite of these children,

planning a diet that meets their nutrient needs becomes a challenge to parents and care-givers. Inadequate meal planning by parents and care-givers lead to malnutrition which is failing health that results from long standing dietary practices that do not coincides with nutritional needs. Wardlaw and Kessel (2011), malnutrition is the fact behind the global phenomenon of infant and child normality that WHO claims to be high in Nigeria (<http://www.who.org>). Even though parent and care-givers provide food and snacks, the quantity, and variety of such foods depend much on such factors as socio-economic and educational status of the parents. What about those children of nursery school age whose parents cannot afford sending to school? Parents do not place emphasis on quantity, quality and variety of foods they give to their children. As established by Wardlaw and Kessel (2011), there is no rapid growth during this period compared to infancy. However, this period usually results in various forms of malnutrition if children are not fed with nutrient-dense food as their appetites decreases. This period is a time when children exhibit variant eating behaviours Parent and other care-giver should be able to follow their children and those under their care respectively with patience so that they would be able to feed them appropriately for a better growth and development. Furthermore, pre-school children are characterized by their rapid growth (ages 2-5 years). These children are very active and this call for high nutrient needs. It is at this stage that under nutrition in the form of kwashiorkor, marasmus, anaemia and xerophilamia is not common (Obidiegwu, 2010). According to standing committee on nutrition United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF 2012), there are more than 150 million under-weight preschool children worldwide and more than 200 million stunted children. In fact, this figure of underweight and stunting is the tip of the iceberg. Suboptimal growth may affect many more children.

Stunting is linked to mental impairment. Even though improvement is made on children nutrition, it has been estimated that one billion children will be growing up by 2025 with impaired mental development. United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund UNICEF (2012). In the related development, numerous studies from developing countries (Nigeria) show that stunting is closely linked to impaired mental development even after allowing for the relationship of both stunting and poor mental development with socio-economic deprivation. WHO (2014) reported that evidence from developing and industrialized countries suggest a fundamental link between maternal and early childhood under-nutrition and an increased susceptibility in adult life to non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as diabetes mellitus, heart diseases and hypertension. These diet-related diseases including cancers are already major public health challenge for developing countries. Nutritional problem found in Pre-school children is Iron deficiency anemia, which appears in children between the ages of 6 and 24 months. Fisher, Robert and Yu Ma (2014) stated that preschoolers tend to explore their environment and noted that even good eaters are sometime more interested in exploring than eating. Hence, this period calls for more attention on parents and care-givers with respect to the kind of food served and the frequency of eating to ensure that all nutrients are available and in adequate amounts to sustain growth and development at their age.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Nutritional problem found in pre-school children is iron deficiency anaemia which appears in children between the age of 6 and 24 months. According to Cohen (2018), it can lead to decreases in both stamina and learning ability because the oxygen supply to cells decreases. Another effect is lowered resistance of diseases.

Wardlaw et al. (2020), reported constipation as one of the three nutrition related problems found in pre-school children. Even though constipation may be associated with other diseases, young children could experience it, and that it could be unrelated to any medical condition. Another nutrition related

problems as reported by Wardlaw and Kessel (2011), is dental caries. It was later reported that infants are prone to early childhood caries, which can lead to excessive tooth decay.

In addition to this problem, malnutrition has been report to be common feature of this stage in life even in places and families with abundant sources of food. These problems are simply preventable if adequate care is taken by parents and other care-givers to prepare adequate meals and ensure that their children eat as much as possible. Increased and widespread knowledge by parents and other care-givers in respect of what, how and when to feed their children to maintain high nutritional status will ultimately lead them in subsequent years into adulthood through adolescence.

One of the societal issues that predispose children to under nutrition is poverty. However, rapid improvement in nutrition will not necessarily be a direct result of economic growth. Even though there is an ongoing women development in society that cuts across all spheres of woman life, there are still cases of infant malnutrition which is one of the leading cause of infant mobility and mortality in Nigeria (<http://www.unicef.org>) in spite of the above, there are still pockets of cases of malnutrition such as iron deficiency anaemia in diverse place in Nigeria. Based on the above mention situation, the problem of this work is to assess the nutritional status of nursery school children in Obudu Local Government Area Cross River State, using anthropometric measurement and clinical signs.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to impact more knowledge on mothers and child care-givers towards the nutritional status of nursery school children in Obudu Local Government Area of Cross River State. The study intends to:

- (a) Assess the socio-economic and educational status of the parents of the nursery school children in Obudu L.G.A
- (b) Carry out the anthropometric measurement of the nursery school children, namely ; weight/height, weight/age and height/age of nursery school children in Obudu L.G.A
- (c) Visually inspect the children for any obvious clinical signs and symptoms of malnutrition using the criteria for inspection such as paleness of the tongue and lips, scantiness and fluffiness of the hair, protrusion of the stomach, flattened buttocks, and presence of oedema and general fitness of the children. In Obudu L.G.A

1.3. Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

- (a) What are the socio-economic and educational status of the parents of the nursery school children in Obudu L.G.A ?
- (b) What is the nutritional status of nursery school children using anthropometric measurement weight/height, weight/age, and height/age in Obudu L.G.A ?
- (c) What are the obvious clinical signs and symptoms of malnutrition such as using criteria for inspection of Nursery Schools children in Obudu L.G.A ?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study used a descriptive Survey approach as research design and it was considered suitable because it helps to study people's attitudes, character and motivate them.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The study was carried out with informed oral consent, anonymity, and confidentiality of the respondents. The data was collected with strict compliance regarding ethical demands of respondents;

data protection management as required in research studies.

2.2. Area of the Study

The research was conducted out in Obudu town. Which is located in Cross River State, Nigeria.

2.3. Population and Sample

The target population for the study considered all the nursery school children 2-6 years old and their mothers/care givers selected in 30 nursery schools in Obudu L.G.A of Cross River State.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

Structured questionnaire was used for the mother/care givers of the nursery school children. The children were also measured using height – for age measuring instrument anthropometric height scale reading (reading in 0 -1cm)

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The total number 200 copies of questionnaire were administered to respondents by the researcher interpretation was made to those that were not educated. The complete questionnaire were collected immediately from the respondent by the researcher. The questionnaire was administered within an interval of three weeks.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The data collected were analyzed using means, standard deviation, the anthropometric measurement and clinical signs were analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS)

2.7. Anthropometric Measurements

Weights of the children were obtained using a portable body weight measurement scale. Height measurement was obtained using measuring apparatus (tape on vertical wood in cm).

2.8. Clinical Examination

The children were usually inspected by the researcher for obvious clinic signs and symptoms on the children.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* What are the socio-economic and educational status of the parents of the nursery school children in Obudu L.G.A ?

Table 1: Socio -economic and educational status of the parents of the children studied

Parameter	F	%
Educational FSLC	3	15
Senior School Cert	4	20
Tertiary Institute	10	50
No formal education	3	15
Age of (yrs.) 20-29	5	25
Mother 3-39	11	55
40-49	4	20
49 – above	Nil	Nil
Marital Married	13	65
Statues of Divorced	5	25
Mother Widow	2	10
Parents Farmer	4	20
Occupation petty trader	7	35
Civil Servant	5	25
Skilled labour	3	15

Under employed	1	5
Size of 2-4	10	50
Family 4-7	10	50
7-10	Nil	Nil
10-above	Nil	Nil
Monthly ₦ 6000 – 8000	11	55
Income ₦ 8000 – 20,000	2	10
Above ₦ 2000	4	20
Below ₦6000	3	15

Table 1 showed the Socio-economic and educational status of the parent of the children studies out of the mother (20) interviewed, the majority (85%) had formal education while only 15% had no formal education. It showed that the majority of the mothers (80%) were in the 20 - 39 years age bracket whereas 20% were within 40 – 49 years of age. In terms of marital status, it revealed that 65% of the mothers were married, 25% were divorced and 10% were widows. The occupation of the mothers showed that the majority (95%) had a means of livelihood while only 5% were unemployed. The result further revealed that 50% each of the families had family size of 2-4 and 4-7. It also showed that 55% of the mothers 8000-20,000 per month, 20% earned above 20,000 per month, while 15% earned below 600 per month.

3.2. Research question two: What is the nutritional status of nursery school children using anthropometric measurement weight/height, weight/age, and height/age in Obudu L.G.A ?

Table 2: Mean Anthropometric Characteristic of the children studies based on sex.

Characteristics	Male	Female	T-Value	P-Value	Result
	Mean + SD	Mean + SD			
Age (Months)	50.65+1810	52.29+77.19	0.466	0.642	NS
Weight (KG)	17.65+5.27	18.11+4.80	0.455	0.650	NS
Height (CM)	104.33+15.13	106.13+ 15.13	0.596	0.552	NS
Weight (KG) for Age Z- Score	0.03+1.43	0.47+1.35	1.616	0.109	NS
Height (CM) for Age Z- Score	0.23+2.41	0.69+243	0.950	0.344	NS
Weight for height Z Score	0.02+1.89	0.17+1.82	0.516	0.608	NS

Values are mean + standard deviation of measurement from 102 children studied.

P-value less than 0.05 indicates significant difference (PL0.05)

NS = not significantly different between male and female (P70.05)

Table 1, Showed that the mean age (months), weight (KG) and Height (CM) were not significantly different (P70.05) between the male children and the female children. Furthermore, the Z-scores for weight – for – age, Height-for- age and weight-for- height of the male children were not significantly different (P70.05) from that of the female children.

3.3. Research question three: What are the obvious clinical signs and symptoms of malnutrition such as using criteria for inspection of Nursery Schools children in Obudu L.G.A ?

Table 3: Prevalence of wasting, stunting and underweight among the male and female children

	Male	Female		Total	X ² P-Value		
	F%	F%		F%			
Weight for wasted	6	5.9	5	0.466	0.642		
Height status normal	33	32.4					
overweight	7	6.9					
Height Stunted	6	5.9	5	4.9	11	10.8	
Age Status Normal	32	31.4	34	33.3	66	64.7	2.44 (0.296)
Tall	8	7.8	17	16.7	25	24.5	NS
Weight for Under Weight	4	3.9	2	2.0	6	5.9	
Age Status Normal	39	38.2	48	47.1	87	85.3	63 (0.44)
Overweight	3	2.9	6	5.9	9	8.8	NS
Total	46	45.1	56	54.9	102	100.0	

P- value less than 0.05 indicates a significant association or influence

NS = Not Significantly associated

Table 2 showed that among the 102 children studied, 10.8% were wasted the prevalence of wasting among the male children was 5.9% while 4.9% of the female children were wasted. However set of the children did not significantly influence ($P > 0.05$) the weight for – height status of the children. It further showed that among the children, 10.8% were stunted. Again the prevalence of stunting among the male children was 5.9% whereas 4.9% the child female children were stunted sex of the child did not significantly influence ($P > 0.05$) the height – for age status of the children. Structured questionnaire was used for the mother/caregivers of the nursery school children. The children were also measured using height-for-age measuring instrument anthropometric height scale reading (reading in 0-1 cm).

3.4. Table 4: Feeding patterns of the Children studied

Parameter	F	%
No of feeding per day		
Once	None	
Twice	4	20.0
Thrice	8	40.0
More than four times	8	40.0
Skipping meal		
Yes	15	75.0
No response	5	25.0
Reason for skipping meal		
Do not like food given	5	25.0

Not enough food in the house	2	10.0
Sleeps before food is served	3	15.0
Are not offered food	2	10.0
Do not request for food	3	15.00
Source of drinking water		
Rain	7	35.0
Stream water	3	75.0
Pipe borne water	4	20.0
Well water	6	30.0

Table 4 showed that the majority (80%) of the children eat between three times and more than four times a day while only 20% eat twice a day. It further showed that the majority (75%) skip meals for a number of reasons ranging from do not like food given (25%), not enough food in the house and are not offered food (10% each); sleeps before food is served and do not request for food were 15% each. Sources of drinking water for the children revealed that 35% were rain, 15% were stream water, 20% were pipe borne water while well water was 30.0%

The eating habits of the children indicated the 47.2% of the food preference of the children were energy-giving for including beverages which lends support to the fact that energy-giving foods constituted 45.5% of the food the children always ate whereas growth-promoting food (protein) constituted 18.2%. These habits could probably have been established in families due to availability of mostly carbohydrate foods. That was why the result showed that energy –giving food constituted the majority of the food given daily to the children. The major reason for this was poor socio-economic and educational status of the mothers which indicated that even though the majority of them had a means of livelihood, 50% of the families had large family size of children. This is an economic burden on the parents especially the mothers who were mainly within the active years of 20-39 years with low income.

4. Conclusion

This study has showed that the nutritional status and health of some of the nursery schools was poor due to food insecurity which is now a global problem.

This poor status was due to poor socio-economic and education background of their parent is ranging from poor income, lack of knowledge of food nutrients. These have resulted in the children not eating what they should eat both quantity and quality.

The following recommendations were made in view of the finding of the study conducted.

Parents should be highly encouraged to have and maintain farms and gardens to enable them provide adequately for the nutritional needs of their children, this help to ensure household food security. Mother and child health clinic personnel should educate and enlighten parents (mothers) on the nutritional needs of their children. The concept of producing complementary food using available foodstuffs should be highly encouraged, and lastly, as much as possible, children should be made to eat 2-3 meals including 2-3 servings of snacks to enhance their nutritional status.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interests.

Author Contributions

COO and BIA contributed to the conceptualization and design of the research and to the analysis and interpretation of the data. COO contributed to the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. All authors critically revised the manuscript, agree to be fully accountable for ensuring the integrity of the work, and read and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article: further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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References

- Casadei, K., & Kiel, J. (2022). *Anthropometric Measurement*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Cohen A.R (2018) Choosing the best strategy to prevent childhood iron deficiency. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 281, 2247-2253. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.281.23.2247>
- Fisher, Robert J. & Yu Ma (2014). The Price of Being Beautiful: Negative Effects of Attractiveness on Empathy for Children in Need. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 41, 436-450 <https://doi.org/10.1086/676967>
- McBean, L. D., & Miller, G. D. (1999). Enhancing the nutrition of America's youth. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 18, 563-571. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.1999.10718890>
- Morrison, D., Milani, A., Binzel, R., A'Hearn, M., Bailey, M., Blanco, C., Tichý, M. (2002). Working Group on Near Earth Objects: (Groupe De Travail Pour les Objets Proches De La Terre). *Transactions of the International Astronomical Union*, 25, 139-140. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0251107X00001358>
- Obidiegwu, J., Rodriguez, E., Ene-Obong, E., Loureiro, J., Muoneke, C., Santos, C. & Asiedu, R. (2010). Ploidy levels of *Dioscorea alata* L. germplasm determined by flow cytometry. *Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution*, 57, 351-356. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10722-009-9473-8>
- UNICEF (2012). Report on the Nutritional Health of Children in the Developing Nations. Retrieved from <https://data.unicef.org/topic/nutrition/child-nutrition/> (accessed August 4, 2022)
- Wardlaw, & Kessel (2011). *Perspective in Nutrition*. McGraw-Hill College; 5th edition; 5th Edition
- Wardlaw, G.M, Hampl, J.S. & Disilvesto, R. A (2004). *Perspective in nutrition*, 6thedu, New York, McGraw-Hu companies.
- Wardlaw, J. M., Benveniste, H., Nedergaard, M., Zlokovic, B. V., Mestre, H., Lee, H., & Black, S. E. (2020). Perivascular spaces in the brain: anatomy, physiology and pathology. *Nature Reviews Neurology*, 16, 137-153. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41582-020-0312-z>
- WHO (2014). A progress report on Malnutrition in the development world. Retrieved from <http://www.who.gov> (accessed August 4, 2022).
- World Health Organization (2010). *Iron deficiency anaemia: assessment prevention and control: a guide for programme managers* Geneva. Retrieved from https://apps.who.int/nutrition/publications/en/ida_assessment_prevention_control.pdf (accessed August 4, 2022)

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